

Synthesis of benzoylformic acid

Gui-yin Li^{a,b}, Yu-ren Jiang^{b*}, Ke-Long Huang^{b*}, Zuo-zhou Liu^b and Ping Ding^b

^aHuman Vocational College of Science and Technology, Changsha 410118, P. R. China

E-mail : jiangyr@mail.csu.edu.cn, klhuang@mail.csu.edu.cn Fax : 86-731-8879850

^bCollege of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Central South University, Changsha 410083, P. R. China

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Abstract : A new route for preparing benzoylformic acid (phenylglyoxylic acid) was studied by benzene as the starting material after Friedel-Crafts reaction with acetic anhydride, oximation by isopropyl nitrite, then hydrolysis by hydrochloric acid and sodium nitrite. Calculated on the basis of acetophenone, the final yield is 57.5%. The suitable experimental conditions were also discussed.

Keywords : Benzoylformic acid, benzene, oximation, hydrolysis.

Introduction

Benzoylformic acid (phenylglyoxylic acid) is an important intermediate for the drugs of thromboxane synthetase inhibitors as well as antihypertensive agents¹⁻³. Benzoylformic acid belongs to α -ketoacids and is easy to oxidize, decarboxylate and deketone. So it is difficult to prepare benzoylformic acid. Oxidation of mandelic acid with potassium permanganate is the usual method of synthesizing benzoylformic acid with the yield of 50 to 72%⁴. Erich Baer *et al.*⁵ studied a convenient method of preparing benzoylformic acid by oxidation of mandelic acid with lead tetraacetate. Calculated on the basis of mandelic acid, the overall yield of benzoylformic acid is 67%. But mandelic acid is very expensive. The second method to prepare benzoylformic acid is hydrolysis of benzoyl cyanide with concentrated hydrochloric acid⁶, the yield of benzoylformic acid is 73–77%. Though the yield was high, benzoyl cyanide synthesis by the reaction of benzoyl chloride and potassium cyanide which would lead to many problems such as the pollution of the environment, the safety of laborer, etc. Another method to obtain benzoylformic acid is to oxidize styrene with potassium permanganate in alkaline solution⁷. The commercial availability of pure styrene makes this an economical source of benzoylformic acid, but the yield is low, only 55%.

Selective oxidations of methyl or methylene groups in an α -position to a carbonyl group are known to be viable routes for obtaining α -ketoacids⁸⁻¹⁰. However, the conversion acetophenone to benzoylformic acid with reagents such as selenium dioxide, thionyl chloride, mixtures of

nitric and nitrous acids in organic solvents, potassium permanganate in potassium hydroxide, gives the product in low yield together with furazan-2-oxide, phenylglyoxal and benzoic acid. Marzianom N.C^{11,12} showed that benzoylformic acid can be obtained in the reaction between acetophenone and a nitrosating agent at 25 °C in the narrow acidity range between 72 and 80% (wt) H₂SO₄. The yield varied from 60–94%. But the experimental condition was not suitable to the industrial manufacture, and those reagents gave many environmental problems.

In this paper, a new route was suggested by using benzene as starting material to synthesize benzoylformic acid (Scheme 1). Firstly, benzene reacted with acetic anhydride to obtain acetophenone by Friedel-Crafts reaction, then acetophenone was converted into isonitrosoacetophenone by isopropyl nitrite, and then isonitrosoacetophenone was hydrolyzed under the reaction of the proton acid and sodium nitrite. The final product was obtained at a high yield and it's easy to operate.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Benzoylformic acid was prepared by three important stages from acetophenone. Oxime was prepared in the first stage, and was hydrolyzed into aldehyde intermediate in the second stage and then oxidized into the acid in the third stage. The reaction conditions of oxidation of acetophenone by isopropyl nitrite and hydrolysis by acids were important factors to the total yield.

Alkyl nitrite can oxidize active CH_2 into oximes. Any alkyl nitrite may be employed in this reaction, but isopropyl nitrite was preferred, since the low boiling point of the isopropyl alcohol facilitates its removal¹³. The reaction conditions of oxidation of acetophenone by isopropyl nitrite are very important to the yield. Table 1 showed the effect of the ratio of acetophenone : isopropyl nitrite on the oxidation of acetophenone. When the ratio of acetophenone : isopropyl nitrite was 1 : 2.0, the highest yield (78.2%) was obtained. The temperature must be controlled below the boiling point of the nitrite.

Table 1. Effect of the ratio of acetophenone : isopropyl nitrite on the oxidation of acetophenone

Ratio of acetophenone : Isopropyl nitrite	Temperature (°C)	Yield (%)
1 : 1.0	15	46.8
1 : 1.2	15	48.3
1 : 1.5	15	52.8
1 : 1.8	15	68.5
1 : 2.0	15	78.2
1 : 2.3	15	62.5
1 : 2.0	25	66.6
1 : 2.0	35	50.5
1 : 2.0	0	54.8

The isonitrosoacetophenone can be hydrolyzed by proton acid into diacetyl, then the diacetyl was oxidized by sodium nitrite into carboxylic acid. Diacetyl can't be isolated from the solution. In fact, many proton acids can be employed in this reaction, such as hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, phosphoric acid, etc. Table 2 showed some important factors in the hydrolysis reaction. The optimum reaction conditions were the molar ratio of acetophenone to H^+ to NaNO_2 was about 1 : 3.6 : 1.5, the reaction temperature and time were 80 °C and 4 h, and the yield was 73.5%.

During the reaction, oximes would convert into other compounds in acidic media. For example : Beckman rearrangement and the decarboxylation reaction. Those conversions were unavoidable, but in the

Table 2. Hydrolysis of oxime to aldehyde by proton acids

Acid	Ratio of acetophenone : H^+ : NaNO_2	Temperature (°C)	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
HCl	1 : 2.4 : 1.0	50	4.0	30.2
HCl	1 : 3.0 : 1.5	50	4.0	45.6
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	50	4.0	57.9
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	60	4.0	56.1
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	70	4.0	63.2
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	80	4.0	73.5
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	90	4.0	65.5
HCl	1 : 3.6 : 1.5	80	4.5	67.8
H_2SO_4	1 : 1.8 : 1.0	50	4.0	53.3
H_2SO_4	1 : 1.8 : 1.5	50	4.0	32.0
H_2SO_4	1 : 2.4 : 1.5	50	4.0	36.2

proper conditions as suggested above, the vice reaction can be minimized.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial sources. The IR spectra were recorded with KBr discs in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} on Nicolet AVATAR360 Fourier-transfer infrared. ^1H NMR spectra were determined from solutions in CDCl_3 with an EM 360 A (300 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal reference. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) in CDCl_3 . Melting points were measured on a WRS-1B melting instrument.

Isopropyl nitrite was synthesized according to the references¹³. The yield of product is 89.7% (b.p. 39–40 °C/745 mm Hg). Isopropyl nitrite was stored in a refrigerator.

Acetophenone was prepared from benzene reacted with acetic anhydride through Friedel-Crafts reaction according to the references¹⁴ (yield : 93%. m.p. 19.2 ~ 20.8 °C).

Preparation of isonitrosoacetophenone^{15,16} :

A three-necked, round-bottomed flask is provided with a reflux condenser, addition funnel, liquid sealed mechanical stirrer, and a gas delivery tube which extends as far as possible into the flask. Dry hydrogen chloride is introduced through the tube during the whole reaction time. The reaction temperature keeps at 15 °C. A mixture solution of 12 g (0.1 mol) acetophenone, 30 ml ethyl ether is placed into the flask. 3 g freshly distilled isopropyl nitrite (total : 12 g) (0.2 mol) is then added from the addition funnel. After addition of the first portion of isopro-

pyl nitrite the reaction mixture becomes brown, and after several minutes, light yellow. At this point a second portion of nitrite is added and a similar color change takes place; further additions are made until all the isopropyl nitrite has been added. The reaction mixture warms up, and the ether begins to reflux gently. Dry hydrogen chloride is introduced until 20 mins later. The rest solution is poured slowly, with stirring, into a mixture of 50 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and about 20 g ice. The yellow shaggy solid of isonitrosoacetophenone are filtered with suction. Yields : 78.2%, m.p. 125.7~131.4 °C (reported 126~128 °C¹⁷). Recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 128.3~128.8 °C. IR spectra : 3308 cm⁻¹, 3296 cm⁻¹ (-NOH), 3085, 3040 cm⁻¹ (Ar-H), 2950 cm⁻¹ (C-H), 1704 cm⁻¹ (-C=O), 1598, 1578, 1546 cm⁻¹ (C=C in benzene), 1480 cm⁻¹ (C=N), 980 cm⁻¹ (N-O). ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) δ : 9.13 (1H, s), 8.1 (1H, s), 7.76 (2H, d), 7.50 (1H, m), 7.42 (2H, m).

Preparation of benzoylformic acid¹⁸ :

In a 250 ml, three-necked, round-bottomed flask fitted with a mechanical overhead stirrer, thermometer, and addition funnel. 14.9 g (0.1 mol) of isonitrosoacetophenone, 20 ml of H₂O, 18 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid were then added. The mixture solution is heated up to 80 °C, 21.9 g 50% NaNO₂ (0.15 mol) is slowly added into the solution, the reaction needs 4 hours. Then the solution is saturated by NaCl, extracted with three 30 ml portions of CH₂Cl₂ and washed with 10% Na₂CO₃. A white crystal can be obtained after drying over sodium sulfate, distilled under reduced pressure. Benzoylformic acid was purified by repeated crystallization from carbon tetrachlorides. 11.5 g of benzoylformic acid was dissolved in 17 ml of warm carbon tetrachloride and the solution was cooled to -5 °C. The colorless and well-crystallized acid was filtered off, washed with a small volume of cold carbon tetrachloride and dried *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide. m.p. 64.4–65.5 °C; reported m.p. 65–66 °C¹⁹. Yields : 73.5%; IR spectra : 3002 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1735 cm⁻¹ (-C=O), 1662, 1594, 1576 cm⁻¹ (C=C in benzene), 1203, 1178 cm⁻¹ (C-O). ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) δ : 9.89 (1H, s), 8.32 (2H, d), 7.70 (1H, m), 7.54 (2H, m).

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References

1. W. B. I. Wright, J. B. Press, P. S. Chan, J. W. Marsico, M. F. Haug, J. Lucas and J. Tauber, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1986, **29**, 523.
2. B. Atrash, D. M. Jones and M. Szelke, EP : 530167, 1993-3-3.
3. I. L. A. Sircar, WO : 9206081, 1992-04-6.
4. B. B. Corson, A. R. Dodge, S. A. Harris and R. K. Hazen, *Organic Synthesis*, 1928, **8**, 68.
5. E. Baer and M. Kates, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1482.
6. T. S. Oakwood and C. A. Weisgerber, *Organic Synthesis*, 1944, **24**, 16.
7. C. D. Hurd, R. W. McNamee and F. O. Green, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2979.
8. A. H. Haines, "Methods for the Oxidation in Organic Compounds", Academic Press, London, 1985, Vol. 2, p. 60.
9. K. D. Whang and C. H. Sung, EP : 1097917A1, 2001-9-5.
10. M. G. Johnson and J. P. Turnbull, US : 4013680, 1977-3-22.
11. N. C. Marziano, L. Ronchin and C. Tortato, *Catalysis Today*, 2004, **91**, 225.
12. N. C. Marziano, L. Ronchin, C. Tortato, A. Zingales and L. Scantamburlo, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.* 2005, **235**, 17.
13. W. A. Noyes, *Organic Synthesis*, 1985, **2**, 7.
14. Z. J. Zeng, "Organic Experiment", 3rd ed., Higher Education Press, Beijing, 1995, p. 125.
15. N. Levin and W. H. Hartung, *Organic Synthesis*, 1987, **3**, 25.
16. W. H. Hartung and F. Crossley, *Organic Synthesis*, 1989, **2**, 44.
17. E. R. Alexander, M. R. Kinter and J. D. McCollum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 801.
18. A. Z. Cooper and A. Meister, *Chem. Rev.*, 1983, **83**, 321.
19. B. B. Corson, N. E. Sanborn and P. R. Van, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1623.